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To cite this article: Richard de Groot, Sudhanshu Handa, Luigi Peter Ragno, Tayllor Spadafora & on behalf of the Ghana LEAP1000 Evaluation Team (2020) Child malnutrition, consumption growth, maternal care and price shocks: new evidence from Northern Ghana, Development Studies Research, 7:1, 18-30, DOI: [10.1080/21665095.2020.1722721](https://doi.org/10.1080/21665095.2020.1722721)

To link to this article: <https://doi.org/10.1080/21665095.2020.1722721>

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Child malnutrition, consumption growth, maternal care and price shocks: new evidence from Northern Ghana

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ABSTRACT

Childhood malnutrition remains a significant global health concern. In order to implement effective policies to address the issue, it is crucial to first understand the mechanisms underlying malnutrition. This paper uses a unique dataset from Northern Ghana to explain the underlying causes of childhood malnutrition. It adopts an empirical framework to model inputs in the production of health and nutrition, as a function of child, household and community characteristics. The findings suggest that maternal agency and health contribute to improved health status. Household resources – in the form of consumption – are positively associated with food intake and nutritional outcomes. Simulations show that income growth, improving maternal care and avoiding sudden price shocks have a positive – but rather limited effect – on the reduction of malnutrition in this context. Effects are greater in children under two. Hence, policies that address underlying determinants simultaneously, and target the youngest population of children, could have the largest effect on reducing malnutrition in this population.

ARTICLE HISTORY

Received 28 June 2019
Accepted 24 January 2020

KEYWORDS

Nutrition; health; Ghana; policy simulations

1. Introduction

Malnutrition remains a major public health problem. It is estimated that about 45% of deaths of children under five are linked to malnutrition (Black et al. 2008). More than 160 million children under age five suffer from stunting, or being too short for their age, with the highest rate of stunting worldwide being found in sub-Saharan Africa (SSA) (UNICEF 2013). Stunting results from prolonged periods of malnutrition and exposure to infectious diseases and more than 70% of stunting takes place before a child's second birthday (Leroy et al. 2014). It is widely recognized that children all over the world have the same growth potential in early childhood, given the right conditions (WHO Multicentre Growth Reference Study Group and Onis 2006). Early life growth deficits can lead to deficits in later life outcomes, and stunting in early childhood has been linked to impaired cognitive development, reduced school achievement, lower economic productivity in adulthood and poorer maternal reproductive outcomes (Dewey and Begum 2011).

In Ghana, chronic malnutrition remains a significant public health issue. While Ghana achieved the Millennium Development Goal (MDG) of halving the proportion of children who are underweight and wasted, the reduction in the level of stunting remained off track (UNDP and NDPC 2015). Nearly 19% of children under five are stunted, but levels of stunting are higher for children in rural areas, from poorly educated mothers, and those living in poor households. The Northern region shows the highest prevalence of stunting with a rate of 33% (GSS, GHS, and ICF International 2015).

In order to implement effective policies to address malnutrition, it is imperative to understand the immediate and underlying determinants of malnutrition. A widely recognized framework, depicted in Figure 1, identifies food intake and health status as the two immediate determinants of nutritional status (Black et al. 2008). These immediate determinants are determined by household food security, care for mothers and children and a healthy household environment.

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 Supplemental data for this article can be accessed <https://doi.org/10.1080/21665095.2020.1722721>

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Figure 1. Framework of the immediate and underlying causes of child malnutrition. Source: Adapted from Black et al. (2008).

Poverty is driving the underlying determinants, while basic determinants at the national level include the socio-political context and availability of resources (physical, financial, human, social and natural).

Previous research has concentrated on understanding the immediate determinants of malnutrition: food intake and health status. A systematic review of interventions concluded that feeding interventions, such as promotion of complementary feeding through nutritional education and zinc supplementation, had the highest potential to reduce stunting globally. With 99% coverage, such programs would reduce the global prevalence of stunting for children up to 36 months by 15% and 17% respectively (Bhutta et al. 2008). In combination with several other interventions, including micronutrient interventions and disease control interventions, there is the potential to decrease stunting by one-third (Bhutta et al. 2008). A more recent update of these estimations, using a scale-up of ten interventions to 90% coverage, estimated a 20% reduction in stunting (Bhutta et al. 2013). While this shows large potential, most cases of

stunting would not be eliminated by focusing solely on these immediate determinants. Hence there is a need to further examine how focused interventions on the underlying determinants of malnutrition can reduce child malnutrition. A review of nutrition-sensitive interventions focusing on agriculture, social protection, early childhood development and education concluded that the evidence base is limited, and such interventions require more specific nutrition goals and actions to better fulfill their potential (Ruel and Alderman 2013).

This paper uses a unique dataset from Northern Ghana to study the factors associated with childhood malnutrition, focusing on its underlying determinants. It also simulates several interventions that improve the underlying determinants, to examine their potential role in reducing malnutrition. We make several contributions to the existing literature on child nutrition and public policy. First, many studies focus on one element of the underlying determinants of child nutrition, such as diet diversity (Arimond and Ruel 2004), maternal education (Glewwe 1999; Handa 1999; Chen and Li 2009),

income growth (Haddad et al. 2003) or water and sanitation (van der Hoek, Feenstra, and Konradsen 2002; Checkley et al. 2004). By estimating the framework as one complete model – albeit in two stages – we quantify the underlying mechanisms determining inputs, and the likely pathways contributing to nutritional status. Second, our data is unique as it captures a particularly vulnerable population, namely rural poor households with pregnant women or young infants. Other studies usually depend on national level household data, which limits the possibility of studying a particular group in detail. Third, we estimate the potential and effect size of various interventions and provide suggestions for effective public action.

The paper proceeds as follows: Section 2 describes the data and methods; Section 3 presents findings on the immediate and underlying determinants associated with improved child nutrition; Section 4 simulates several policy interventions to enhance child nutrition; Section 5 discusses the implications of the findings and concludes.

2. Data and methods

Data for this study are derived from the baseline survey of the Livelihood Empowerment Against Poverty (LEAP) 1000 impact evaluation. LEAP 1000 is a cash transfer program targeted at extremely poor households with pregnant women and mothers with children under 12 months in the Northern and Upper East Regions of Ghana. The program is an extension of Ghana's flagship poverty alleviation program LEAP and is implemented by the LEAP Management Secretariat (LMS) and the Department of Social Welfare (DSW) under the Ministry of Gender, Children and Social Protection (MoGCSP). Baseline data for the impact evaluation was collected between July and September 2015 from 1262 prospective beneficiary households and 1235 comparison households in five districts in the Northern and Upper East Regions of Ghana. This paper uses baseline data only, and none of the beneficiary households had yet received a transfer.¹

2.1. Econometric model

It is typical to operationalize the framework of Figure 1 in a health production function. The idea is that the human body is a biological system that 'produces' health using a set of inputs such as food intake and (lack of) illness. The demand for inputs in the production function are usually modeled in a separate specification, since they may be endogenous (Behrman and Deolalikar 1988). One way to circumvent this problem, is to find strong instruments for the inputs. Typically, the prices of foodstuff, the availability of health care or the quality of health care, are used. Should

adequately rich longitudinal data be available, the complete history of inputs can be used (Puentes et al. 2016). However, most datasets are not sufficiently rich to estimate the full production function, and ours is, unfortunately, no exception.² The next best estimation in this case, is the reduced form child health function, based on the underlying model of the utility-maximizing family (Becker 1981; Behrman and Deolalikar 1988). We estimate two types of reduced form equations: the input demand function, and the conditional nutrition demand function.

In these models, the outcome (demand for health inputs or nutrition, h_i) is a function of child characteristics (x_i), parental characteristics (x_p), household indicators (x_h) and community features (x_c):

$$h_i = h(x_i, x_p, x_h, x_c, \mu). \quad (1)$$

Child characteristics include age, sex, birth outcomes, and number of siblings. Household characteristics include maternal characteristics, household size and head of family characteristics. Community features consist of the distance to the nearest health center, water and sanitation facilities, and the prices of common food and non-food items. Our conceptual framework serves as a guide for which community-level factors to include in the input demand models. The health environment only directly influences health inputs, whereas food prices only directly affect food intake. Finally, μ is an error term for unobserved child, household and community heterogeneity, affecting the child's nutritional status and is assumed to be uncorrelated with the x variables in this model. We cluster standard errors at the community level.

We restrict the sample to children aged 6–59 months, for several reasons. First, children under 6 months are recommended to be breastfed exclusively; this limits the number of feeding variables we can include in our models. Second, measurement errors in terms of height are generally larger for children under 6 months, due to the difficulty of accurately measuring infants. Third, stunting typically starts to become a problem when infants are transitioning from breastfeeding to complementary feeding, at 6 months (Shrimpton et al. 2001). We further restrict our sample to children for whom we have full information on all indicators, and children who live in communities in which five or more children were sampled, resulting in a final analysis sample of 2460 children.³

3. Results

3.1. Descriptives

Below is a short description of the explanatory variables used as underlying determinants of child nutrition. Due

to space constraints, the means and standard deviations are presented in Table S1 in the supporting information file.

Educational achievement of mothers is low, with more than 80% never receiving any formal schooling. Nutrition and health knowledge was constructed based on the mother's responses to six questions on child nutrition and health with an average number of correct responses higher than four.⁴ Maternal health could be an important determinant of child health, given the potential of the genetic endowment passed on to offspring. We use a measure of self-reported subjective health, with five response options (poor, fair, good, very good and excellent), which has been found to be a good predictor of future mortality and morbidity (DeSalvo et al. 2006). We dichotomize this indicator into self-reported good, very good or excellent health which was reported by just over three-quarters (76%) of mothers. Agency – measuring decision-making power of the mother in the household – is an aggregate score based on six statements and cut into terciles; low (36% of mothers), middle (40%) and high (24%).⁵

Households are large with mean household size of nearly seven members. Less than 10% of households are headed by a woman, and 80% of household heads never went to school. The mean monthly consumption expenditure per adult equivalent is approximately 92 Ghana cedi (GH¢), which translates roughly into US\$ 0.74 per adult equivalent per day.⁶ We include the natural log of this measure in our analysis to account for the large right-hand tail in the distribution.

Community characteristics consider whether the household has access to improved sanitation facilities, improved sources of drinking water and appropriate hand washing facilities. The dwelling floor type, presence of bed nets, and vaccination coverage are also considered.⁷ For each of these indicators, we calculate the non-self community mean⁸, as it is likely that these indicators are correlated with other household characteristics (Christiaensen and Alderman 2004; Kabubo-Mariara, Ndenge, and Mwabu 2009). About 60% of children live in communities with access to an improved source of water, while only 10% have access to improved sanitation facilities. Appropriate hand washing facilities is even lower at 7%. One-quarter of the houses in these communities has a mud floor. Two-thirds sleep under a bed net and vaccination coverage is 75%. We include the natural log of the distance to the nearest health center for each household, as a measure of access to health services. The average distance to the nearest health center is about 10 km (not shown). The prices of seven common consumption items at the nearest market are matched to the household data.

3.1.1. Food intake and health status

Health status is based on the incidence of three common childhood diseases in the two weeks prior to the survey: diarrhoea, fever and symptoms of acute respiratory infections (ARI). We combine the latter two into a single indicator of non-diarrhoeal illness. To ease interpretation of results, all indicators are coded so that a higher score indicates a more positive outcome (i.e. lack of illness). About 58% of the children had not suffered from diarrhoea, indicating that 42% did experience the disease in the two weeks before the survey. In addition, 30% experienced fever or symptoms of ARI.

Food intake of a single child is notoriously difficult to measure in large-scale field surveys. We proxy the *quality* of food intake by looking at the different food groups proposed by WHO (2010): consumption of iron-rich foods; consumption of grains, roots and tubers; consumption of dairy products; consumption of vitamin A-rich fruits and vegetables; and consumption of other fruits and vegetables. The quality of a child's diet has been linked to nutritional status in many settings (Arimond and Ruel 2004). To assess the *quantity* of food intake, we use meal frequency (whether the child had 3 meals or more). Meal frequency is a strong predictor of energy intake in infants and young children and thus an important input in the production of health (Working Group on Infant and Young Child Feeding Indicators 2006). About two-thirds of children consumed iron-rich food (e.g. (organ) meat, fish or iron-fortified foods); 80% consumed grains, roots or tubers; 21% consumed dairy products; and 70% consumed vitamin A-rich plant foods (such as yellow flesh fruits and vegetables or dark green leafy vegetables). However, less than half of the children received the recommended three or more meals per day.

3.1.2. Nutritional status: height-for-age

We are interested to document the effects of the underlying and immediate determinants on long-term measures of child malnutrition. The appropriate nutritional measure is therefore height-for-age z-scores (HAZ), which has been commonly used as an indicator of overall long-term health and human capital (Victoria et al. 2008). The mean HAZ is -1.28 (SD 1.68), more than 30% of children are stunted ($HAZ < -2$ SD) and 13% are severely stunted (Table 1).

3.2. Estimation results

This section presents results of estimating equation (1), first on the immediate determinants of child malnutrition – food intake and health status – and then on the nutritional

Table 1. Inputs and nutritional outcomes ($N = 2460$).

Variable	Mean	SD	Min	Max
Inputs: Health status				
No diarrhoea in last two weeks	0.58	0.49	0	1
No other illness in last two weeks	0.70	0.46	0	1
Inputs: Food intake				
Consumed iron-rich food yesterday	0.68	0.47	0	1
Consumed grains, roots and tubers yesterday	0.80	0.40	0	1
Consumed dairy products yesterday	0.21	0.41	0	1
Consumed vitamin A-rich fruits and vegetables yesterday	0.70	0.46	0	1
Consumed other fruits and vegetables yesterday	0.11	0.31	0	1
Consumed three or more meals yesterday	0.45	0.50	0	1
Nutritional outcomes				
HAZ	-1.28	1.68	-5.92	5.91
Stunted (HAZ < -2)	0.31	0.46	0	1
Severely stunted (HAZ < -3)	0.13	0.34	0	1

outcome, HAZ. We also test for the joint significance of parental, household and community characteristics respectively in each estimation separately.

3.2.1. Food intake and health status

The results for the eight input demand functions are presented in Table 2. The models are estimated with a probit model, and marginal effects are presented. Note that the community health characteristics are only included for the health input models, while food prices are only included for the food intake equations, to be consistent with the conceptual framework of the study. We present estimates for the full sample of children aged 6–59 months, but also for the subsamples of children aged 6–23 and 24–59 months, as it is likely that these different age groups have different nutritional and health needs. The results for these sub-groups are reported in Tables S3 and S4 in the supporting information file. We focus the presentation and discussion of the results on parental, household and community characteristics.⁹

Parental characteristics have a limited correlation with the demand for inputs. For example, maternal education is only significant in one case: higher maternal education is (weakly) associated with better health status. The mother's age is positively related to the lack of diarrhoea, the lack of other illnesses, and the consumption of iron-rich and vitamin A-rich foods, although the size of the associations are small. The mother's agency has some interesting and puzzling results. While higher agency is strongly associated with better health outcomes, it has a negative association with the demand for dairy products and appropriate meal frequency. Maternal self-reported health status is positively related to both child health indicators, but has no association with the food inputs. Nutritional knowledge has mostly no effect on any of the inputs, except for a small and weakly

significant association with the intake of dairy products. Parental characteristics are jointly significant (at the 10% level) in five of the eight input demand equations: both health indicators, the intake of dairy products, and vitamin A rich fruit and vegetables, and appropriate meal frequency.

Household consumption has positive associations with four of the food inputs. However, it has strongly negative effects on the health status, which seems counter-intuitive, i.e. higher welfare is associated with poorer health outcomes. The magnitude of the associations is relatively small though. For example, a 10% increase in household consumption is associated with a 0.0068 (0.68 percentage points) and 0.0075 (0.75 percentage points) increase in the probability of diarrhoea and non-diarrhoeal disease, respectively. Nonetheless, in order to validate these results, we perform checks with two alternative datasets, the Ghana Living Standards Survey (GLSS) 2012/2013, and the DHS 2014. We also observe a negative association between household consumption (GLSS) or wealth (DHS) and incidence of illness for children under five in these datasets, at least for the lowest two quintiles, which is where most of our households are located (Table S2 and Figure S1 in the supporting information file).

One potential explanation is survival bias if child mortality in the poorest households is higher than in the richer households, and only healthier and stronger children survive in the poorest households. In the Ghana DHS, all forms of child mortality are indeed higher in the lowest quintile, compared to the other quintiles (GSS, GHS and ICF International 2015). In our data too, we observe a negative (though statistically insignificant) relation between child mortality and household consumption (Figure S2 in the supporting information file).

Another potential explanation is the employment status of the mother of the child. If a mother works, she may have less time to care for her child, resulting in increased risk of illness despite higher household income (Sinmegn Mihrete, Asres Alemie, and Shimeka Teferra 2014). To test this, we construct an indicator equal to one if the mother of the child performed any casual or formal work outside the home. The results (not shown but available upon request) indicate that the mothers' employment status is, indeed, negatively associated with both health indicators. However, the coefficient on consumption decreases only by a few decimal points in both equations, remaining strongly significant.

A third potential explanation is that poorer households simply underreport episodes of illness because they are unable to recognize illness, or because they forget. For example, a study in India showed that recall bias for morbidity was higher among poorer households,

Table 2. Marginal effects from probit models on health and nutrition inputs in children aged between 6 and 59 months.

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)
	No diarrhea in last 2 weeks	No other illness in last 2 weeks	Iron-rich food	Grains, roots and tubers	Dairy products	Vitamin-A rich fruits and vegetables	Other fruits and vegetables	Meal frequency (at least 3 per day)
<i>Parental characteristics</i>								
Mother's education (ref = none)								
Some primary	-0.067	-0.015	0.023	-0.028	-0.023	-0.007	0.012	0.036
	0.042	0.042	0.036	0.036	0.024	0.038	0.027	0.035
Primary completed or above	0.018	0.054*	0.039	0.015	0.012	-0.034	0.024	0.009
	0.037	0.032	0.029	0.027	0.025	0.035	0.022	0.034
Mother's age	0.007***	0.005*	0.005*	0.004	0.001	0.005**	-0.001	-0.001
	0.003	0.003	0.003	0.003	0.002	0.002	0.002	0.003
Living with father	-0.072	-0.069	0.036	-0.071	-0.040	-0.048	-0.028	-0.035
	0.054	0.044	0.048	0.046	0.034	0.040	0.028	0.044
Mother's agency (ref = Low)								
Medium	0.119***	-0.006	-0.020	0.022	-0.040**	0.028	-0.024	-0.056**
	0.033	0.025	0.029	0.025	0.017	0.025	0.030	0.026
High	0.147***	-0.001	-0.038	0.016	-0.046***	-0.010	-0.031	-0.094***
	0.036	0.027	0.030	0.029	0.017	0.023	0.029	0.029
Nutritional knowledge	-0.008	0.009	0.007	0.011	0.010*	-0.008	-0.001	-0.013
	0.009	0.009	0.009	0.009	0.006	0.010	0.006	0.009
Self-reported health good/very good/excellent	0.156***	0.147***	0.034	-0.005	-0.013	0.019	0.004	-0.009
	0.021	0.026	0.027	0.022	0.018	0.024	0.017	0.025
<i>Household characteristics</i>								
Log of AE household consumption	-0.068***	-0.075***	0.035*	0.020	0.016	0.033*	0.042***	0.078***
	0.019	0.019	0.021	0.020	0.015	0.019	0.012	0.017
<i>Community characteristics</i>								
Vaccination coverage ¹	0.034	-0.093						
	0.072	0.066						
Improved sanitation ¹	-0.032	-0.167**						
	0.074	0.073						
Improved source of water ¹	0.051	0.064						
	0.049	0.042						
Appropriate handwashing facilities ¹	0.027	0.249*						
	0.120	0.137						
Mud floor ¹	-0.097	0.090						
	0.077	0.062						
Slept under bed net ¹	0.131*	0.023						
	0.078	0.076						
Distance to nearest health center	0.022*	-0.031***	0.038**	-0.013	0.006	-0.002	-0.032***	0.023
	0.013	0.012	0.017	0.012	0.008	0.010	0.008	0.014
Price of Guinea corn/sorghum			0.503**	0.117	-0.159	0.067	0.019	-0.125
			0.209	0.183	0.109	0.167	0.136	0.194
Price of maize			-0.051	-0.132	0.049	-0.161	-0.160	0.216
			0.166	0.154	0.088	0.153	0.105	0.147
Price of millet			-0.120*	-0.147*	-0.016	-0.098*	0.043	0.052
			0.063	0.085	0.036	0.054	0.048	0.062
Price of rice (local)			-0.141*	0.244***	0.068*	0.109	0.011	-0.108
			0.082	0.077	0.038	0.081	0.048	0.082
Price of dried fish			-0.007	0.002	-0.005*	-0.008**	0.003	-0.003
			0.005	0.004	0.003	0.003	0.004	0.004
Price of okro			0.022	-0.044***	0.001	-0.020	-0.000	0.016
			0.018	0.013	0.008	0.015	0.010	0.015
Price of petrol			0.005	0.003	-0.043	-0.110**	0.135***	-0.110*
			0.063	0.059	0.028	0.045	0.043	0.056
Observations	2460	2460	2460	2460	2460	2460	2460	2460
<i>Tests for joint significance (p-value):</i>								
Parental characteristics	0.000	0.000	0.240	0.169	0.039	0.095	0.872	0.054
Household characteristics ²	0.000	0.000	0.082	0.148	0.154	0.010	0.000	0.000
Community characteristics	0.069	0.006	0.000	0.022	0.131	0.000	0.000	0.011

Notes: Cluster-robust standard errors in second row. Additional control variables not reported: child age dummies, sex, twin, birth order and number of siblings, birth interval, household size, share of women aged 12–49, age of head of household, sex of head of household and whether she/he ever went to school. * $p < 0.10$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$. ¹ Non-self community mean. ² Includes household size, share of women aged 12–49, age of head of household, sex of head of household, and whether she/he ever went to school.

especially when recall periods were longer (Das, Hammer, and Sánchez-Paramo 2012). Another study to validate the accuracy of child morbidity data in the

DHS concluded that mothers with low education and from poor household tend to report childhood illnesses less often than richer mothers (Manesh et al. 2008).

The community health characteristics have little explanatory power in the health input equations. Surprisingly, improved sanitation, improved source of water and appropriate hand washing facilities have no effect on the incidence of diarrhoea. Improved sanitation has an estimated negative association with non-diarrhoeal diseases. This is in contrast to research that finds significant associations between access to water and sanitation technologies and child morbidity (Günther and Fink 2010). On the other hand, an improved source of drinking water is not necessarily free of microbial contamination (Bain et al. 2012). The distance to the nearest health center generally yields opposite signs for the two health inputs: for diarrhoea, there is a small but statistically significant positive association i.e. the further away the health center, the more likely a lack of diarrhoea, while for non-diarrhoeal diseases, it is the other way around. The distance to health center is positively associated with the consumption of iron-rich food, and negatively associated with the intake of other fruits and vegetables. This could be due to the remoteness of communities far from health centers, with mostly 'inferior' foods available and perhaps poorer knowledge to identify diarrhoeal diseases. There are only a few significant associations between local prices on health and nutritional inputs. Except for one input (dairy products), the community characteristics, including prices, are jointly significant in the input demand equations.

In the analysis by age group, most of the main results hold, with a few exceptions. For younger children, the negative association of maternal agency with intake of grains remains, but the negative association with meal frequency is no longer significant. The opposite is true for the older cohort (24–59 months). In addition, for the younger children, the negative correlation between household consumption and diarrhoea is no longer significant, but it is for older children.

3.2.2. Nutritional status

The regression results of the conditional demand for HAZ are presented in Table 3. The model is again estimated for the full sample, for the younger cohort (6–23 months) and the older cohort (24–59 months) separately, but results are only reported for the full sample in the main body of the text, whereas results by age group are reported in the supplementary information file, Table S5.

Like the input demand functions, maternal characteristics have very little influence on HAZ in our data, except for a weak but significant and positive association between the mother's age and height. Household consumption is positively correlated with height-for-age, indicating that higher welfare is associated with better

Table 3. OLS regression of child, paternal, household and community characteristics on height-for age (children 6–59 months).

	(1) Height-for-age
<i>Parental characteristics</i>	
Mother's education (ref = none)	
Some primary	–0.167 0.137
Primary completed or above	–0.076 0.109
Mother's age	0.015* 0.008
Living with father	–0.233 0.178
Mother's agency (ref = Low)	
Medium	0.132 0.089
High	0.022 0.103
Nutritional knowledge	0.035 0.028
Self-reported health good/very good/excellent	–0.088 0.094
<i>Household characteristics</i>	
Log of AE household consumption	0.148** 0.062
<i>Community characteristics</i>	
Vaccination coverage ¹	0.392* 0.199
Improved sanitation ¹	0.169 0.277
Improved source of water ¹	–0.083 0.162
Appropriate handwashing facilities ¹	–0.604 0.379
Mud floor ¹	0.204 0.246
Slept under bed net ¹	0.593** 0.286
Distance to nearest health center	0.027 0.057
Price of Guinea corn/sorghum	–0.573 0.591
Price of maize	0.269 0.494
Price of millet	0.063 0.229
Price of rice (local)	0.420* 0.253
Price of dried fish	–0.017 0.014
Price of okro	–0.062 0.050
Price of petrol	0.008 0.231
Observations	2460
R-squared	0.139
<i>Tests for joint significance (p-value):</i>	
Parental characteristics	0.137
Household characteristics ²	0.025
Community characteristics	0.008

Notes: Cluster-robust standard errors in second row. Additional control variables not reported: child age dummies, sex, twin, birth order and number of siblings, birth interval, household size, head characteristics. * $p < 0.10$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$. ¹ Non-self community mean. ² Includes household size, share of women aged 12–49, age of head, sex of head and whether head ever went to school.

growth and development.¹⁰ However, although the association is significant, the magnitude of the effect is small: the coefficients show that a 10% increase in household consumption is associated with a 0.015 SD increase in HAZ. In terms of community characteristics, only the

vaccination coverage and sleeping under bed nets seem to matter for HAZ. With one exception, none of the prices are significant in the model, and distance to the health center has no significant association with HAZ. Household characteristics and community characteristics are jointly significant in the model.

For the younger cohort, there is a negative association of maternal education with HAZ, and the presence of the father in the household also has a negative association. On the other hand, the association of household consumption increases to 0.19 and remains strongly significant. For the older cohort, most of the estimates lose their significance and only the community characteristics remain jointly significant. This may be an indication that most of the changes in nutritional status appear in the first two years of life, consistent with the theory of the first 1000 days.

4. Simulations of consumption growth, improved maternal care and price shocks

In this section, we simulate three possible scenarios and their importance in reducing malnutrition. Due to the large amount of evidence on programs addressing the immediate determinants of malnutrition (e.g. see Bhutta et al. 2008; Bhutta et al. 2013) and the lack of evidence on interventions improving the underlying determinants (Ruel and Alderman 2013), our simulations focus specifically on the underlying determinants of malnutrition, namely food security (proxied by household consumption), care for mothers, and community level prices. The choice of the three possible scenarios is based on the importance of these factors in the determination of immediate determinants and nutritional outcomes and on Ghana-specific interventions or events.

For example, household consumption was found to be significantly associated with seven of the inputs and HAZ and is thus an important factor to consider. Care for mothers, operationalized by agency and self-reported health status, was highly significant in the health input equations, in two of the food inputs, but less so in the HAZ model. Several community prices were significant in the input demand models. In addition, price hikes are not uncommon in Ghana, with food inflation in the vicinity of 10% and non-food inflation over 20%, on annual basis (GSS 2016).¹¹

We simulate three possible scenarios. One cash transfer intervention, equivalent to Ghana's national cash transfer scheme, the LEAP program. The second scenario simulates improvements in the care environment for mothers by increasing her agency and improving her health. The last scenario simulates a sudden increase in prices, for example, as a result of droughts or failed

Table 4. Parameters of simulations.

Simulation	Parameters
(1) LEAP cash transfer	Increase household expenditures by monthly LEAP transfer amounts: 38 for two beneficiaries, 44 for three beneficiaries and 53 for four beneficiaries ¹
(2) Improved care environment	Set agency at 'medium' for mothers with low agency and set self-reported health at 'good' for all mothers
(3) Price increases	Increase all prices by 10%

Notes: ¹ The baseline data includes the exact transfer amount for households enrolled into the LEAP program. For comparison households, we impute the (hypothetical) transfer amount by counting the number of eligible beneficiaries in the household (number of pregnant women and infants, people with a disability, elderly, and orphans) and assigning the transfer amount accordingly.

harvests. Table 4 provides a summary of the parameters for each simulation.

The simulations are estimated using the full models from Tables 2 (for inputs) and 3 (for HAZ). For HAZ, we estimate the predicted changes for the average z-score, as well as the rate of stunting. The actual values are simply substituted by the simulated value in the regression equations, while all other variables in the models are held constant.¹² We then compare the mean values of the outcome indicators as observed in the data, to the predicted mean value when one of the explanatory variables is changed according to the values shown in Table 4. A key assumption is that the variable used for the simulation is exogenous. Our assumptions are strong since it could be that other variables within the model are also affected through our simulations. For example, price changes may also affect household consumption expenditure. The simulations therefore represent a very simplified version of reality.

While we have chosen our simulation scenarios using indicators that are often statistically significant in the models, we acknowledge that the indicators used for the simulations are not significant in *all* of the models. This could be because the indicator is truly zero (i.e. has no effect on the outcome) or because the estimated coefficient is imprecise, meaning that the standard error is simply large, but the coefficient is not necessarily equal to zero.¹³ We assume that the second explanation is more likely in our case. Even if the first explanation is true, the estimated coefficients will be close to zero and will have a negligible effect in the simulations.

Results are reported in Table 5. Increased consumption is simulated to lead to poorer health, due to its negative association in the input demand regression. The predicted change, however, is very small, around two percent. If increases in household consumption go hand in hand with improved knowledge about child health or maternal agency, this effect may be reversed.

Table 5. Simulation results on health and food inputs and nutritional outcomes.

Variable	Base value	(1)		(2)		(3)	
		LEAP transfer		Improved care		Price shock of 10%	
		Prediction	% change	Prediction	% change	Prediction	% change
<i>Health inputs</i>							
No diarrhoea	0.579	0.570 [0.540,0.600]	-1.6%	0.660 [0.625,0.696]	14.0%		
No other illness	0.695	0.687 [0.662,0.712]	-1.2%	0.731 [0.694,0.767]	5.2%		
<i>Food inputs</i>							
Iron-rich food	0.682	0.688 [0.658,0.717]	0.9%	0.683 [0.637,0.730]	0.1%	0.693 [0.642,0.744]	1.6%
Grains roots and tubers	0.804	0.808 [0.780,0.835]	0.5%	0.811 [0.775,0.846]	0.9%	0.816 [0.768,0.864]	1.5%
Dairy products	0.208	0.210 [0.196,0.225]	1.0%	0.191 [0.171,0.212]	-8.2%	0.187 [0.162,0.212]	-10.1%
Vitamin A-rich fruits and vegetables	0.697	0.701 [0.678,0.724]	0.6%	0.712 [0.676,0.747]	2.2%	0.635 [0.589,0.682]	-8.9%
Other fruits and vegetables	0.110	0.115 [0.096,0.134]	4.5%	0.103 [0.077,0.128]	-6.4%	0.159 [0.118,0.199]	44.5%
Meal frequency	0.448	0.458 [0.430,0.486]	2.2%	0.425 [0.393,0.458]	-5.1%	0.405 [0.357,0.452]	-9.6%
<i>Nutritional Outcomes</i>							
HAZ	-1.279	-1.259 [-1.349,-1.169]	1.6%	-1.252 [-1.365,-1.139]	2.1%	-1.274 [-1.462,-1.087]	0.4%
Stunted	0.307	0.304 [0.283,0.325]	-1.0%	0.300 [0.274,0.326]	-2.3%	0.324 [0.275,0.372]	5.5%

Notes: Results are based on the models from Tables 2 and 3. Predictions of stunting are based on probit models using the same independent variables as the HAZ model. 95% prediction interval in square brackets.

On the other hand, increased household consumption is estimated to improve the quality and quantity of child food intake, although the increases are only marginal – in the range of one percent – for most of the inputs. Improvements in consumption have a modest, yet positive effect on nutritional status of 1.6%. Similar findings are reported by Alderman and Garcia (1994) for Pakistan, who find a simulated reduction of 3% on stunting as a result of a 10% increase in household consumption. In Ethiopia, a simulated increase in income of 2.5% for 15 years would reduce stunting by 4% (Christiaensen and Alderman 2004).

Improved care is simulated to increase the probability of no diarrhoea by 14% and the likelihood of no other illness by 5.2%. Moreover, we observe positive simulated changes in the consumption of iron-rich food, grains, roots and tubers. In contrast, the simulated effect of improved care on the intake of fruits and vegetables that are not rich in vitamin A, is negative. It could be that this is a substitution effect, as vitamin A-rich foods are important for growing children. There is also a negative simulated change in the probability of eating three meals per day. The simulated effect of improved care on nutritional outcomes is positive, but also modest. The effect on HAZ is similar in size as the increase in consumption, though the simulated decrease in the rate of stunting is somewhat larger at 2.3%.

The simulation of a price shock estimates that intake of non-vitamin A rich foods increases when prices

increase, while the effect of a price shock is negative, or close to zero, for the other food inputs. It could be that this food group largely consist of foods that households consider ‘inferior’ and to which they resort when prices of preferred, and perhaps higher quality, food items rise. A price shock worsens nutritional status. For example, while our price shock simulation shows no effect on the mean z-score for height-for-age, it has a 5.5% simulated effect on the probability of being stunted. Note that the simulated price shock is a one-time event. If there are continuous price shocks over a relatively small time period, the effects on nutritional status could be even worse.

Again, we perform the same simulations for each of the two age groups separately and report the results in the supporting information file (Tables S6 and S7). For the youngest cohort, the negative effects of consumption on health become negligible, while the positive effects of consumption on the food inputs and nutritional outcomes are similar as in the full sample. Improved care has a larger simulated effect on health status with an increased probability of nearly 19% on the lack of diarrhoea and six percent increased probability of not having another illness. It also has a slightly larger effect on the nutritional status than in the full sample, with an estimated 3.5% reduction in stunting. For the older cohort, as expected, the simulations show less potential, with lower effects of the simulated interventions on inputs and outcomes. However, price shocks seem to be more important in this age group,

as a 10% price increase is simulated to yield a nearly 11% increase in the rate of stunting.

5. Discussion and conclusion

Previous research has investigated the potential of policies primarily addressing the immediate determinants of malnutrition, health status and food intake (Bhutta et al. 2008; Bhutta et al. 2013) and has suggested that such interventions yield a maximum reduction of stunting in the range of 20%–35%. To further examine what may contribute to the reduction of stunting, we estimated a health production function and modeled interventions aimed at underlying determinants to assess their relative importance in a particularly unique population – children in poor households with pregnant women or women with infants. Since the production of child nutrition is highly complex, any model that is able to shed light on the underlying mechanisms is useful to inform policy to improve child nutritional status (Alderman and Garcia 1994).

Our results show that parental characteristics were only weakly correlated with the immediate determinants of malnutrition, food intake and health status. We found almost no association of maternal education and maternal knowledge with food intake and health status. The mother's level of agency is related to improved health, but also associated with reduced demand for dairy products and appropriate meal frequency. Mothers with higher agency may have more time commitments during the day, such as running a household business.¹⁴ Hence, higher maternal agency will likely only lead to nutritional improvements through the health pathway; not through the food intake pathway. Maternal poor health has a negative association with their children's health as well, potentially showing a genetic link, physical difficulties in taking care of children or as a result of living in a poor health environment. The significantly positive – though small – correlation of the mother's age with four of the inputs, provides evidence that delaying child birth could have important benefits for children's health and nutrition.

Household consumption has a negative association with health status, but generally a positive association with food intake. The negative correlation with health is also observed in other datasets, and may be explained by survival bias, the mother's occupation, or the inability of ultra-poor households to identify and recall illnesses among their children. In addition, Figure S1 in the supporting information file shows that while the association between consumption and health may be negative for the lowest consumption quintile, there is an overall

positive association between consumption and health as soon as consumption reaches a certain threshold. Since our sample primarily includes extremely poor households, it is likely that these households have not yet reached this threshold.¹⁵ However, the intake of each food group also increases with household consumption and for three of the food groups and in terms of meal frequency, this relation is significant. This suggests that when household consumption grows, the quality and quantity of food intake can improve too.

The community health characteristics have little explanatory power for both health status and food intake. The distance to the nearest health center is often used as an indicator for the cost of accessing health care and, as such, may influence decisions related to seeking care. However, the relationship between distance and our input and outcome indicators is weak. The prices of common staples are considered important community factors that may influence food intake. The results for these indicators are not coherent; sometimes positive and sometimes negative. However, it is important to differentiate between net food producers and net food consumers: the producers benefit from higher prices, to the detriment of consumers. Most households in our sample are subsistence farmers. However, we have no information on the size of their harvests, and therefore cannot determine which of the two groups they belong to, and more importantly, whether this makes a difference in terms of input demand.

We find little evidence that parental characteristics are important in the demand for nutrition. While previous research has found significant effects of maternal education on height or HAZ (Handa 1999; Smith and Haddad 2000; Christiaensen and Alderman 2004; Chen and Li 2009; Aslam and Kingdon 2012), we find no association between the highest educated female in the household and the immediate determinants, nor a direct association with children's nutritional status. Rather, we find that the association with the mother's agency is a better indicator of her ability to improve nutritional outcomes for her children, especially through improving the health status of the child. Prior research has shown that improving health and nutritional knowledge may be more important than increasing educational achievement (Glewwe 1999). Previous work in Ghana showed that care practices were significantly related to HAZ, although quality of care was measured in a different way across studies, and not using a similar framework to that of our study (Ruel et al. 1999; Nti and Lartey 2008; Amugsi et al. 2014). Household consumption is positively correlated with HAZ, showing that increased resources can help to improve child nutritional status. It is important

to note that the estimated coefficients on household consumption are relatively small. For example, in a 12-country study, the estimated coefficient of log per capita consumption on weight-for-age (WAZ) ranged from 0.14 to 1.20, with a mean of 0.54 and a median of 0.47 (Haddad et al. 2003). While our study uses a different nutritional indicator, they are closely related and our estimate of 0.148 (Table 3) is at the lower bound of this range.¹⁶

A limitation of this study is the cross-sectional nature of the data. We were not able to address the endogeneity of the inputs in the health production function and we therefore estimated reduced form demand functions. Others have used longitudinal data to instrument the endogenous inputs with prior inputs, and lagged weight and height (De Cao 2011; Handa and Peterman 2016; Puentes et al. 2016). This study is further limited by the regional scope and poverty status of the sample, potentially affecting the external validity of the results. Finally, while the uniqueness of the sample is an asset because it allows the study of a particularly vulnerable population, the homogeneity in the sample may be the reason that certain relations not show up. For example, the non-existent relation between sanitation and health, and between maternal education and nutritional status, may be due to the lack of variability in the indicators. The simulations in this paper represent a very simplified version of reality in which only one component changes while everything else remains constant. This may not hold true in reality and careful *ex-post* analysis of interventions are needed to examine actual effects and pathways.

Globally, researchers have called for a more integrated approach to address malnutrition, in the form of nutrition-sensitive programming (Ruel and Alderman 2013). Due to the complex nature of child growth, no single program working in isolation will be able to sustain considerable impacts on malnutrition. This is supported by our findings, which indicate that public policy – which is able to increase consumption, improve care for mothers, and keep down inflation – is likely to have a positive, yet modest, effect on nutritional inputs and outcomes in a population of poor, rural households. Hence complementary interventions, which work in tandem to address multiple underlying determinants simultaneously, may have larger potential. In addition, policies aimed at younger children are found to be more effective in this context. This is in line with global evidence that targeting interventions during the first 1000 days of life yields the largest benefit (Bhutta et al. 2008). Finally, while our simulations provide important insights into the *likely* effect of an intervention, further research is needed to estimate the *actual* impacts of policy on malnutrition, using rigorous evaluation

designs. Such research should also focus on the effect of policy on the underlying mechanisms that determine malnutrition, in order to understand how public policy can contribute to these various determinants.

Notes

1. For more details on the study design and baseline analysis, see the baseline report (UNICEF OoR, ISSER, UNC-CH, and NHRC 2016).
2. Previous drafts of this paper attempted to identify and use instruments to estimate the full production function, but several sets of instruments (prices, distance to health facilities, non-self community means of inputs) were found too weak in predicting the inputs in the demand equation.
3. This is due to the calculation of community means for certain variables, further details below.
4. Questions related to the importance of exclusive breastfeeding, immediate breastfeeding after birth, duration of breastfeeding, foods rich in iron, foods rich in vitamin A and knowledge about home treatment of diarrhea.
5. Agency is measured on 5-point Likert scale, with the following six statements: Your life is determined by your own actions; You have the power to make important decisions that change the course of your own life; You have the power to make important decisions that change the wellbeing of your children; You have the power to make important decisions that change the wellbeing of your household; You are capable of protecting your own interests within your household; You are capable of protecting your own interests outside of your household (e.g. in the community, in groups in which you participate). Internal consistency among the statements is high, with Cronbach's alpha of 0.77.
6. Exchange rate at 15 September 2015: GH¢ 1 = US\$ 0.2448337399.
7. Definitions of improved water and sanitation facilities are based on standard classifications according to WHO and UNICEF (2016).
8. The non-self community mean is the mean value of the indicator, averaged over all observations in the community, excluding the value of the indicator for the household itself.
9. Full regression output is presented in the supporting information file, Tables S8 – S11.
10. Some would argue that household consumption is endogenous in this specification. We test for endogeneity of household consumption using assets and household characteristics as identifying instruments (first-stage robust *F*-test: 11.4) and find no evidence of endogeneity based on the Durbin-Wu-Hausman test (*p*-values >0.10, results available upon request).
11. We choose to focus on price increases rather than decreases. Price decreases can be realized when certain food or non-food items are subsidized. However, due to the consistent evidence that government subsidies are generally regressive (Wodon and Zaman 2010) and governments throughout Africa, including Ghana, are removing rather than instating subsidies, we do not consider the potential of price decreases.
12. We use Stata's margins, `at(...)` command for this exercise.

13. Typically, standard errors increase if the residual variance in the model is large (Angrist and Pischke 2009). Note that the R-squared in our models is relatively low (and hence the residual variance large), yet this is common in nutritional analysis. In addition, standard errors increase with low variability in the underlying variables, which is the case with the community characteristics, as the non-self means are based on dummy indicators.
14. Further inspection of the data shows that agency is indeed significantly higher among mothers who are also responsible for a household enterprise, which may compromise the time they have to care for their children.
15. The GLSS figure suggests that this threshold is around the logged consumption value of 6, which less than 1% of the households in our sample achieve.
16. Note that our consumption measure is *per adult equivalent* and not *per capita*. If we were to use per capita consumption, our estimates would be slightly lower than presented here.

Acknowledgements

This research is part of a collaborative research program between: UNICEF Office of Research – Innocenti; UNICEF Ghana; the Institute of Statistical, Social and Economic Research (ISSER) at the University of Ghana; and the Carolina Population Centre at the University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill. We are grateful for funding from the Government of Canada and USAID for this research. We thank Richmond Aryeetey, Michael Cichon, Franziska Gassmann, Kalle Hirvonen, Luisa Natali, Nyasha Tirivayi, the anonymous reviewers and participants in seminars at UNICEF Ghana and Maastricht University, for their valuable suggestions and Sarah Marchant for copy-editing the text.

Disclosure statement

No potential conflict of interest was reported by the author(s).

Funding

This work was supported by Canadian International Development Agency [grant number PO7060382 D0000306-001]; United States Agency for International Development [grant number GHA-G-00-07-00007].

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